

MS26

First FAIR school for ENVRI community data centre staff completed

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1 Introduction and background

The objective of Work Package 6 is to provide training to ENVRI and key ENVRI stakeholder groups about the FAIR principles, how to implement them in RI services and data management activities at data centre level, how to evaluate the degree of implementation using FAIR metrics, as well as relevant legal and policy requirements.

While Task 6.1 is concerned with preparing and disseminating training resources, the main responsibility of Task 6.2 is to organise and provide training for data centre staff from RIs (both inside and outside of ENVRI-FAIR) on FAIR implementation.

The primary target group for the training is staff at the ENVRI data centres, especially those concerned with data management and service architecture. This group will benefit both from self-paced study activities and from tutorial sessions organized e.g., in connection to project collaboration meetings and Webinars. A second important target group for the training is the staff of data centres of key local, regional and national institutions dealing with environmental data. In fact, many RIs are concerned with coordinating and disseminating data products (and services) produced by external contributors. These data provider communities will also benefit from training in FAIR practices. To promote this, tutorial sessions will be organized in connection to domain-specific conferences.

1.1 First FAIR winter school for ENVRI community

Here we describe the first FAIR winter school for ENVRI community held online on January 11-22, 2021.

1.1.1 Planning and preparations

1.1.1.1 Target groups

The main target groups are the staff at ENVRI data centres (in order to encourage the collaboration among the different RIs), researchers and PhD students.

1.1.1.2 Choice of theme and methodology

The gap analyses performed by WP6 Task 6.1, and reported on in deliverable D6.1 [Hellström 2019], indicated that ontologies, terminologies, semantic linking and metadata schema and standards are topics to be of high importance and priority within the RIs in ENVRI-FAIR. A three-day webinar program was organized in July-September 2020, introducing the main topics of the winter school (the use of FAIR data in the ENVRI Community and for environmental and Earth science research) with theoretical presentations, exercises and discussions. We decided to build up the program of the first FAIR winter school around the topic “ENVRI-FAIR Resources: Access & Discoverability” with the following story line:

- how to discover resources;
- how to create resources;
- how to access resources;
- how to create containers and publish resources.

The main decisions related to the training methodology have been:

- training slots of 2 hours (including breaks) only in the morning;
- live lectures with live questions/polls to increase the interaction among participants;
- introductory session on the first day of the school to let participants socialise and introduce themselves (round table + ice breaker questions);
- breakout rooms after each learning slot to socialise, for exercise, etc.

1.1.1.3 Goals

The aim of the school is to present the state-of-the-art technologies relevant to FAIRification of services. Moreover, starting from real-life use cases, it aims at encouraging the adoption of new technology to enhance data centre functionality and enable new knowledge-exchange networks for ENVRI data professionals.

To receive the certificate of attendance, participants had to prepare a written report and a short presentation on a valid and concrete use case.

1.1.1.4 Selecting instructors

When selecting the instructors for the school, we wanted to have contributions both from experts that are familiar with the ENVRI community organisations and their terminology- related requirements, as well as from specialists from other disciplines contributing with their perspectives. Based on a combination of their credentials and positive experiences from the 2018 and 2019 summer schools organised by LifeWatch ERIC and ENVRIplus, we decided to invite as teachers: Antonio José Sáenz-Albanés and José María García-Rodríguez for the semantics part; Ute Karstens, Claudio D'Onofrio, Karolina Pantazatou, and Ida Storm for the VREs, Data Analysis & Visualisation topic; Nicola Fiore and Lucia Vaira for the resource access tools aspects and finally Zhiming Zhao for the Cloud computing topic.

Here below a short bio for each teacher is presented.

Antonio José Sáenz-Albanés: is the ICT e-Infrastructure Operations Coordinator of LifeWatch ERIC. He received a Diploma of Advanced Studies of the Official Postgraduate Program in Engineering and Technology of the Information of the University of Seville. He has 29 years of experience in IT in both the private and public sectors. He was for ten years project manager of the "Centro de Gestión Avanzada" (CGA) for IT-supported educational centres in Andalusia. From its inception and planning to fully operational capabilities (hundreds of thousands of distributed computers, thousands of distributed servers and centres, and more than a million daily users.) Deploying the complete ITIL services stack, standards-based security operations, large-scale continuous integration and deployment of software, services and hardware, and implementing DevOps operations. He was for ten years CTO of a private company, responsible of all the ICT teams (~250 in-house and world-wide distributed) managing every aspect of production and operations such as recruiting, training, strategic selection of technologies and partners, development and services methodologies, (ISO 9001:2000 using RUP-agile, ITIL, ISO 27000, CMMi) and the management of the project portfolio. Also, he coordinated the R+D+I and defined the strategy and partner selection. He deployed several virtual research environments: nation-wide electric grid planning, improvement and adaptation of the biological station of Doñana to LifeWatch, and scenario-based water innovation and research laboratory (continental waters management). He was also Associated Lecturer in the Languages and Information Systems Department of the University of Seville.

José María García-Rodríguez: received the M.Sc. degree (Hons.) in computer science and software engineering from the University of Seville, Spain in 2008 and the Ph.D. on technology and software engineering from the same University in 2012. From 2006 to 2013, he was a Research Assistant with the University of Seville. From 2012 to 2015, he was a Postdoc Researcher and Assistant Professor with the Semantics Technology Institute of the University of Innsbruck, Austria. In 2015, he re-joined the University of Seville as Assistant Professor, and since 2019 he has been an Associate Professor with the Applied Software Engineering Group, Smart Computer Systems Research and Engineering Lab, Research Institute of Computer Engineering, University of Seville, Spain. He has published more than 20 articles as conference papers, workshop papers, technical reports and journal articles. His research focus is on blockchain, semantic web technologies, service-oriented architectures and linked data.

Ute Karstens is a researcher at Lund University working at the ICOS Carbon Portal. She holds a PhD in Atmospheric Sciences and has more than 20 years of experience in analysis and modelling of atmospheric processes, including trace gas transport modelling and inverse modelling for the estimation trace gas fluxes. At ICOS Carbon Portal she is responsible for the coordination of elaborated products based on ICOS measurement data and services to support ICOS scientists.

Claudio D'Onofrio is a data scientist at Lund University working at the ICOS Carbon Portal. He has a MSc degree in human computer interaction and a PhD in engineering. He has 20 years of working experience in Information Technology within the private and public sector. In his current role the focus

is on data life cycle, data FAIRness, provenance and tracking and corresponding ontologies for meta data. Further he is leading the development of a python library to simplify access to ICOS meta data, data and observations.

Karolina Pantazatou is a junior scientific programmer at ICOS Carbon Portal, Lund University. She holds a BSc in Informatics and a MSc in Geo-informatics. She has worked as a project assistant, a scientific programmer and a GIS engineer in various interdisciplinary projects focusing on climate change, remote sensing, spatiotemporal demographic analysis and city planning. She has held workshops on how to use GIS-tools and Python-programming for researchers, PhD students and university students. At the Carbon Portal, she is developing user friendly Jupyter notebooks that process and analyse ICOS data products, targeted for education and research.

Ida Storm is a project assistant at Lund University working at the ICOS Carbon Portal. She holds a BSc in Geography/Environmental Studies and a MSc in Geographical Information Systems. She is currently also working part-time at Gothenburg University's Center for Digital Humanities and has worked in various interdisciplinary projects where GIS is a component. At the Carbon Portal, she is developing user friendly Jupyter notebooks based on ICOS data and services to support ICOS scientists.

Nicola Fiore is the ICT Coordinator of the LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre. He is Dr. Eng. Computer Science and PhD in Computer Engineering. He has 17 years of working experience in IT, in the field of the design and development of Information Systems in both the private and public sectors, and 10 years of accredited professional experience in the area of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Bioinformatics research. His research activities include the definition of common policies, models and e-infrastructure to optimise technological implementation; definition of workflows; and coordination, harmonisation, integration and interoperability of data, applications and other services. He is one of the members of the Vocabulary Services Interest Group leading the Ontology Market Place working group in the framework of the Research Data Alliance.

Lucia Vaira is the Web Portal Officer of the LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre. She is a Computer Engineer and received her Ph.D. from the University of Salento in 2016. Her research interests include (meta)data modelling, data warehouses, bioinformatics, and all aspects related to the main issues existing when dealing with data (security, quality, incompleteness, inconsistency, integrity, uncertainty, etc.). She has more than 5 years of experience in training and education for courses dealing with information systems, databases and information security. She is author of more than 30 scientific publications and serves as Program Committee member of several workshops and conferences in the Computer Science field.

Zhiming Zhao is an assistant professor at University of Amsterdam (UvA). He leads the "Quality Critical Distributed Computing" research team in the group of Multiscale Networked Systems (MNS) at the System and Networking Lab (SNE). His research interests include big data management, Cloud and edge computing, software engineering, and blockchain. He leads the development support WP in ENVRI-FAIR and the VRE development in the "LifeWatch-ERIC Dutch Virtual Laboratory Innovation Center". He is also the UvA PI in CLARIFY, ARTICONF, SWITCH and several other projects.

1.1.1.5 Training contents

The details of the training contents have been decided by the instructors in dialogue with the WP6 core team. The instructor team therefore settled on a combination of introductory lectures and teacher-led demonstrations. For practical reasons, we could only accommodate 30 participants in total. The selection of participants was based on a mix of criteria, including motivation and use case descriptions.

The school has been organised over a two-week period, on average dedicating around 40 hours in total (including preparations). It has been structured around daily activities, with scheduled lectures and presentations in the mornings (09-11), followed by associated group and individual work time (11-12).

During the first week, we have had the opening session, in which the ENVRI-FAIR project and the WP6 have been shortly introduced. The lectures were on the following two topics:

- **Semantics:** this lecture introduced basic concepts about semantics and how it can enrich data resources and increase its FAIRness, covering Linked Data; machine-actionable FAIRness through semantic technologies; how to apply semantics to the research data lifecycle. Moreover, security and additional aspects have been considered together with recommendations to

consider before developing a RESTful API, an overview of REST API Authentication types and the best practices to secure the REST APIs.

- VREs, Data Analysis & Visualisation: this lecture introduced the fully integrated web application at ICOS Carbon Portal, using the example of the atmospheric transport model STILT. Teachers presented a full life cycle for an 'on demand' model run and the result visualisation. Moreover, they showed how to use the results to create a new data product. A hands-on workshop followed to create a simple timeseries plot comparing STILT results with observational data and creating an interactive map for the station location.

An unsupervised session (2 hours) has been organised at the end of the week in order to let students collaborate in the assignments (divided in groups or individually).

In the second week of the school, we had the lectures of the following two topics:

- resource access tools: this lecture introduced basic aspects and definitions related to metadata, types of metadata, metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies. Moreover, an overview of the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue has been presented in order to show how resources (datasets, services, workflows, etc.) can be published on a catalogue;
- cloud computing: this lecture introduced how to develop and operate data management services in cloud environments. In particular, by using examples from the ENVRIplus and ENVRI-FAIR projects, the teacher demonstrated the basic steps to run a legacy application in cloud, to develop native cloud applications, to automate the application deployment, and to auto-scale a runtime application.

Another unsupervised session (2 hours) has been organised in the middle of this second week in order to let students collaborate in the assignments (divided in groups or individually) and to prepare the report and the final presentation for the last day of the school (divided in groups or individually).

1.1.2 Implementation

1.1.2.1 *Selecting the date and venue*

Due to the COVID-19 emergency, the planned summer school, initially scheduled for July 10-15 2020 has been transformed into a winter school and hence postponed in January 2021.

In order to introduce the main topics of the winter school, a three-day webinar program has been organized in July-September 2020 with theoretical presentations, exercises and discussions. Details about the “Towards ENVRI Community International Winter School programme and the teachers are available on the LifeWatch ERIC website (see <https://www.lifewatch.eu/web/guest/towards-envri-winter-school>).

The winter school took place online on January 11-22, 2021. We used the GoToMeeting platform for the lectures and the Wonder tool (<https://www.wonder.me>) for breakout rooms and unsupervised sessions. Moreover, to collect polls, data and opinions from participants we also used Mentimeter (<https://www.mentimeter.com>).

1.1.2.2 *Advertising the event*

The event has been advertised on the ENVRI community website (see <https://envri.eu/event/envri-community-international-winter-school-on-data-fairness/>) and on the LifeWatch ERIC website (see https://www.lifewatch.eu/all-news/-/asset_publisher/BU9HdfPGXPak/content/envri-community-winter-school/10194), and also spread out via newsletters and social media accounts. In addition, information about the event was spread outside of the project to both ENVRI Community organisations and external networks, including research data management-related mailing lists. After the end of the school has been also published a final report on the LifeWatch ERIC website (see https://www.lifewatch.eu/all-news/-/asset_publisher/BU9HdfPGXPak/content/envri-community-international-winter-school-2021/10194) and on the ENVRI-FAIR website (see <https://envri.eu/students-from-all-around-the-world-participated-in-envri-community-international-winter-school-2021/>)

1.1.2.3 Participants

For practical reasons, we decided to accommodate 30 participants in total, being it an adequate number for networking, groups, etc. The selection of participants was based on a mix of criteria, including motivation and use case descriptions.

Registrants were asked to provide contact details, as well as to indicate their affiliation and their address, to send them a winter school gadget (see the picture below).

Figure 1: School gadget

A total of 33 registrations have been received, indicating a strong interest in the theme of the school. Around 30 persons in total attended the training sessions. The majority of the participants came from research infrastructures participating in ENVRI FAIR, while the rest and the others were from universities and other research organisations.

Here below we have compiled an overview of the participants in terms of country of origin, research infrastructure and position/job title.

Nationality	Count	Research Infrastructure	Count	Position/Job title:	Count
Italy	12	LifeWatch	5	Technical staff	11
Spain	5	ICOS	4	Staff of RI	7
France	2	University of Bologna	3	PhD Student	7
Belgium	3	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn	3	Academic	5
Germany	2	DANUBIUS	2	Master Student about to start a PhD	2
Greece	1	Instituto Español de Oceanografía	2		
Venezuela	1	EPOS	1		
Czech Republic	1	eLTER	1		
Nigeria	1	Importance of Data to poverty reduction	1		
China	1	EISCAT_3D	1		
Sweden	1	PEEX	1		
Mexico	1	PNRA	1		
Slovenia	1	ACTRIS	1		
		Fondazione Gianni Benzi	1		
		CMCC	1		
		University of Granada	1		
		CNR	1		
		UniPA	1		
		ZRC-SAZU	1		
		MNCN-CSIC	1		

Figure 2: Participants' overview

1.1.3 Post-event activities

1.1.3.1 Disseminating course materials

All the slides used during the lectures have been converted to PDF format. All lectures have been recorded and to simplify the access to the specific sessions of interest, the recordings have been split into parts and saved as MP4-format video files.

All these materials have been uploaded in the ENVRI Community Training Platform (see the training course page at <https://training.envri.eu/course/view.php?id=52>).

Moreover, a learning object has been created in the ENVRI Training Catalogue (see the record with the respective metadata at <https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/course/47>).

1.1.3.2 Event evaluation

A feedback form including 14 questions has been prepared in order to let participants to leave their comments and suggestions about the school. The resulting feedback is quite positive and several suggestions can be taken into account for the next training events.

Appendix A is for the feedback form questions and analysis.

1.1.3.3 Lessons learned

The ENVRI Community International Winter School has been the first completely online event organized under the ENVRI-FAIR label.

In spite of the distance, we gave plenty of chances to get participants together and bring community relationships together.

A lot of space was given to the discussion and participants had the opportunity to contribute with their own work.

In order to serve the ENVRI community in the best possible way, a high priority for WP6 will be to maintain a high level of quality, both in terms of the topics covered and the methods by which they are presented. It is very important to evaluate the training events, looking at what worked well and what could be improved.

For the future we have learned that:

- virtual meetings represent a great challenge, especially as regards the use of content and capturing the attention of remote participants;
- coordination between instructors is essential to avoid gaps and / or overlaps. This was achieved through videoconferencing and exchanging draft materials via email in the weeks leading up to the event;
- consider more space for practice with the supervision of the teachers.

We used for the first time the Wonder platform, a virtual event space where people can meet and talk both for social events (welcome, coffee break, breakout rooms for exercise, etc.).

Participants enjoyed the Wonder meeting room even if it is not easy to socialize in an online meeting without knowing the participants previously. But the discussions among participants were both pleasant and productive.

1.2 Webinar series in preparation of the winter school

As already described above, due to the COVID-19 emergency and the restrictions for travelling to and from Italy, our planned summer school, initially scheduled for July 10-15 has been postponed until January 2021. But, in the meanwhile, we decided to organize a three-day webinar programme, with the aim to introduce the main topics of the winter school with theoretical presentations, exercises and discussion.

1.2.1 Planning and preparations

1.2.1.1 Target audience

The main target group are ENVRI-FAIR project partners data centre staff, but the webinar was open to anyone interested in.

1.2.1.2 *Choice of theme*

In order to introduce the main topics of the winter school (the use of FAIR data in the ENVRI Community and for environmental and Earth science research) we decided to build up the webinar programme on the following topics:

- cloud computing and application development for research infrastructures;
- workflows orchestration and execution;
- an introduction on Jupyter.

1.2.1.3 *Selecting speakers*

Based on a combination of their credentials and positive experiences from the 2018 and 2019 summer schools organised by LifeWatch ERIC and ENVRIplus, we decided to invite as speakers: Zhiming Zhao for the Cloud computing topic; Nicola Fiore and Lucia Vaira for the workflows orchestration and execution topic, Claudio D'Onofrio and Karolina Pantazatou for the introduction to Jupyter.

Here below a short bio for each speaker is presented.

Zhiming Zhao Dr Zhiming Zhao is an assistant professor at University of Amsterdam (UvA). He leads the "Quality Critical Distributed Computing" research team in the group of Multiscale Networked Systems (MNS) at the System and Networking Lab (SNE). His research interests include big data management, Cloud and edge computing, software engineering, and blockchain. He leads the development support WP in ENVRI-FAIR and the VRE development in the LifeWatch-ERIC Dutch Virtual Laboratory Innovation Center. He is also the UvA PI in SWITCH, ENVRIplus, ARTICONF and several other projects.

Nicola Fiore is the ICT Coordinator of the LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre. He is Dr. Eng. Computer Science and PhD in Computer Engineering. He has 17 years of working experience in IT, in the field of the design and development of Information Systems in both the private and public sectors, and 10 years of accredited professional experience in the area of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Bioinformatics research. His research activities include the definition of common policies, models and e-infrastructure to optimise technological implementation; definition of workflows; and coordination, harmonisation, integration and interoperability of data, applications and other services. He is one of the members of the Vocabulary Services Interest Group leading the Ontology Market Place working group in the framework of the Research Data Alliance.

Lucia Vaira is the Web Portal Officer of the LifeWatch ERIC Service Centre. She is a Computer Engineer and received her Ph.D. from the University of Salento in 2016. Her research interests include database modelling, data warehouses, medical informatics, and all aspects related to the main issues existing when dealing with data (security, quality, incompleteness, inconsistency, integrity, uncertainty, etc.). She has more than 5 years of experience in training and education for courses dealing with information systems, databases and information security. She is author of more than 30 scientific publications and serves as Program Committee member of several workshops and conferences in the Computer Science field.

Claudio D'Onofrio is a data scientist at Lund University working at the ICOS Carbon Portal. He has a MSc degree in human computer interaction and a PhD in engineering. He has 20 years of working experience in Information Technology within the private and public sector. In his current role the focus is on data life cycle, data FAIRness, provenance and tracking and corresponding ontologies for meta data. Further he is leading the development of a python library to simplify access to ICOS metadata, data and observations.

Karolina Pantazatou is a junior scientific programmer at ICOS Carbon Portal, Lund University. She holds a BSc in Informatics and a MSc in Geo-informatics. She has worked as a project assistant, a scientific programmer and a GIS engineer in various interdisciplinary projects focusing on climate change, remote sensing, spatiotemporal demographic analysis and city planning. She has held workshops on how to use GIS-tools and Python-programming for researchers, PhD students and university students.

At the Carbon Portal, she is developing user friendly Jupyter notebooks that process and analyse ICOS data products, targeted for education and scientists.

1.2.1.4 Training contents

The details of the training contents have been decided by the speakers in dialogue with the WP6 core team.

The webinar programme has been organised over three meetings in three different days and each webinar was two hours long (including break).

The first webinar has been introduced by a welcome and opening session, in which the ENVRI-FAIR project and the WP6 have been shortly introduced.

Here below the detailed scheduling of the webinar series:

- July 13th 2020 10:00 – 12:00
Cloud computing and application development for research infrastructures
In this webinar, we discussed the basic concepts of cloud computing, including virtualization, containerization, service models, and cloud application development. We also discussed how clouds can support data management and scientific workflows in the research infrastructures via examples from ENVRIplus and ENVRI-FAIR projects.
- July 14th 2020 10:00 – 12:00
Workflows Orchestration and Execution
In this webinar, we introduced methodologies and tools to design, develop and execute scientific workflows for data curation and analysis. In particular, the Node-RED orchestrator has been presented and some didactical examples from LifeWatch Italy showcases has been discussed.
- September 22nd 2020 10:00 – 12:00
An introduction on Jupyter
In this webinar we presented a case study on how to use a Jupyter Hub with Python Notebooks as to disseminate research data to the public, policy makers, and scientists. The Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, measuring greenhouse gas concentrations and fluxes. The curated data sets are linked to a persistent identification and are public available. The data portal (ICOS Carbon Portal) further provides services for online collaboration and education. This webinar has been structured into three parts: 1) Automation of Infrastructure; 2) Data Access; 3) Dissemination and Collaboration. In a nutshell, we showed how we use ansible playbooks to create virtual machines, where we assemble docker images to run a Jupyter Hub and the final user interface as a docker container. For shared access and collaboration, we use the underlying Linux infrastructure to create users and groups to fine tune access. Secondly, we have presented how we implemented access to the available data sets and their properties: the conventional way and direct access with a proprietary python library. The last part has given an overview of services, applications, notebooks and visualisations with examples tailored to different audiences.

1.2.2 Implementation

1.2.2.1 Selecting the date and venue

The webinar program has been organized in July-September 2020 with theoretical presentations, exercises and discussions. Details about the “Towards ENVRI Community International Winter School programme and the teachers are available on the LifeWatch ERIC website (see <https://www.lifewatch.eu/web/guest/towards-envri-winter-school>).

We used the GoToWebinar platform for the first two webinars in July and Zoom platform for the webinar in September.

Moreover, to collect polls, data and opinions from participants we also used Mentimeter (<https://www.mentimeter.com>).

1.2.2.2 Advertising the event

The event has been advertised on the ENVRI community website (see <https://envri.eu/event/webinar-towards-envri-community-international-winter-school-data-fairness/>) and on the LifeWatch ERIC website (see https://www.lifewatch.eu/all-news/-/asset_publisher/BU9HdfPGXPaK/content/towards-the-envri-community-winter-school/10194), and also spread out via newsletters and social media

accounts. In addition, information about the event was spread outside of the project to both ENVRI Community organisations and external networks, including research data management-related mailing lists.

Since the first two webinars had short time to promote the event, for the last webinar we sent again the email by using the Redmine system and, moreover, we exploited the ICOS Science Conference held online in September 15-17 to advertise the event. This brought a higher number of registrations (see next section).

1.2.2.3 Participants

For the first two webinars in July, we had an average of 20 participants. In particular, considering the job title, we had:

- July 13th (cloud computing): 18 participants
 - Technical staff: 6
 - Staff of RI: 5
 - Academic: 5
 - PhD Student: 2
- July 14th (workflows): 23 participants
 - Technical staff: 10
 - Staff of RI: 7
 - Academic: 5
 - PhD Student: 1

For the last webinar, we had 122 participants:

- Technical staff: 34
- Staff of RI: 49
- Academic: 30
- PhD Student: 10

1.2.3 Post-event activities

1.2.3.1 Disseminating course materials

All the slides used during the lectures have been converted to PDF format. All webinars have been recorded and to simplify the access.

All these materials have been uploaded in the ENVRI Community Training Platform (see the training course page at <https://training.envri.eu/course/view.php?id=46>).

Moreover, a learning object has been created in the ENVRI Training Catalogue (see the record with the respective metadata at <https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/course/43>).

1.2.3.2 Event evaluation

A feedback form including 15 questions has been prepared in order to let participants to leave their comments and suggestions about the webinar programme.

We received very few feedbacks for the first 2 webinars. That's why we decided to encourage more the feedback submission at the end of the event in the last webinar, from which we received 12 answers.

Despite the low number, the resulting feedback is quite positive and several suggestions can be taken into account for the next training events.

Appendix B is for the feedback form questions and analysis.

1.2.3.3 Lessons learned

For these webinars, we have learned that:

- virtual meetings represent a great challenge, especially as regards the use of content and capturing the attention of remote participants;
- coordination between instructors is essential to avoid gaps and / or overlaps. This was achieved through videoconferencing and exchanging draft materials via email in the weeks leading up to the event;

- to optimize the possibilities of a positive educational outcome, the choice of an appropriate platform is very relevant. Indeed, we experienced that even if GoToWebinar has been thought exactly for webinars, a platform like Zoom configured in "web meeting" style, and thus allowing for easy inter- and intra-participant interactions is better with respect to a webinar-style environment that by definition is optimized for mostly one-way "lectern education" with strictly moderated participant interaction.
It is something strictly related to this type of learning activity (targeting data centre staff who are not just learning something new but should also be able to form a contact network for continued work afterwards).

1.3 Appendix A: winter school feedback

Rating questions:

Descriptive questions:

- Which are your top three take-aways from the school?
- What did you most appreciate or enjoy about the school?
- Please let us know how we could improve!

1.4 Appendix B: webinar series feedback

Evaluation of ENVRI-FAIR webinar "Introduction to Jupyter" held on 22 September 2020

1. How did you learn about the webinar?

12 svar

3. How do you rate the relevance of the training for your current work?

12 svar

2. How do you rate the overall satisfaction with the training?

12 svar

4. How do you rate the presentations?

12 svar

5. Given the topic, this training was:

12 svar

7. What did you most appreciate or enjoy about the training?

6 svar

- Good overviews, both of how to set up a Jupyter instance and on different use cases!
- enough time for question, easy to follow steps in presentations,
- The idea to propose live example
- general overview
- The possibilities to offered
- It was as announced an introduction!

6. In your opinion, the level of difficulty of the training was:

12 svar

8. Please let us know how we could improve!

6 svar

- Maybe have more interactivity with the audience, like quizzes etc to keep the audience's attention at top throughout? But it was good to have several planned breaks!
- slow down practical examples- and pause a bit on each figures so we can ensure what is shown
- make sure that the online examples work
- perhaps a little longer and deeper training
- Practice
- n/a

9. Which is your profession or role? (Select all that apply)

12 svar

11. Did the training give you a good overview over how dockers can be used to set up Jupyter instances?

12 svar

Specific questions on dockers, notebooks and Jupyter:

10. Do you use dockers?

12 svar

12. Have you worked with Jupyter?

12 svar

13. If no previous experience with Jupyter, did this training give you a good introduction to what can be achieved using Jupyter?

11 svar

15. What programming language would you prefer the notebooks to support?

11 svar

14. Do you think notebooks are a good choice for promoting your work/data products to different target audiences?

12 svar

